

Combating Periodontitis through Vaccination: A Review of Emerging Immunological Strategies

Running title: Periodontal Vaccines: Current Advances and Challenges

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Abstract

Periodontal disease is a chronic inflammatory condition caused by microbial dysbiosis and host immune response, leading to progressive destruction of the supporting structures of the teeth. Conventional therapies such as mechanical debridement and antimicrobial strategies offer only temporary control and do not prevent recurrence. In recent years, periodontal vaccination has become a promising adjunct for the prevention and management of periodontitis. Several literatures were analyzed, including preclinical and clinical studies focused on vaccine

candidates targeting key periodontal pathogens, predominantly *Porphyromonas gingivalis*, *Aggregatibacter actinomycetemcomitans*, and *Tannerella forsythia*. Numerous periodontal vaccines have demonstrated immunogenicity and partial protective effects in animal models, with several strategies showing promise in reducing bacterial colonization and modulating destructive immune responses. However, translation to human application remains limited due to challenges such as antigenic variability, delivery systems, and the complexity of the host–microbiome interaction. This review provides a comprehensive overview of current advances in periodontal vaccine development, examining key antigens, vaccine platforms, immunization strategies, and the immunopathology of periodontitis that underpins vaccine design.

Keywords: Periodontitis, Vaccine, *Porphyromonas gingivalis*, Immunotherapy, Oral microbiome, Mucosal immunity

INTRODUCTION:

Periodontitis is a chronic inflammatory condition that affects the supporting structures of the teeth, including the gingiva, periodontal ligament, cementum, and alveolar bone. They are initiated by the accumulation of microbial dental plaque, which harbors a complex biofilm of pathogenic bacteria. The periodontal disease progression is not only influenced by microbial virulence factors but also by the host's immune and inflammatory responses. The oral function and quality of life may be severely impacted if periodontitis is left untreated, as it can result in attachment loss, tooth mobility, and ultimately lead to tooth loss. The global burden of periodontal disease remains high despite improvements in oral hygiene awareness and advances in treatment strategies, highlighting the need for alternative preventive and therapeutic approaches.¹

Traditionally, mechanical debridement and adjunctive antimicrobial therapy have formed the cornerstone of periodontal disease management. However, these methods have limitations, including incomplete removal of subgingival plaque, antibiotic resistance, and the potential for recurrence due to persistent microbial reservoirs. Moreover, the polymicrobial nature of periodontal infections complicates targeted therapeutic approaches. In this regard, periodontal vaccination against important periodontal pathogens presents a novel and promising avenue for periodontitis prevention and management. The concept of periodontal vaccination seeks to stimulate the host immune system to recognize and neutralize specific bacterial antigens, thereby reducing colonization and preventing the cascade of inflammatory destruction that characterizes the disease. By encouraging the host's immune system to identify and combat particular bacterial antigens, periodontal vaccination aims to lessen colonization and stop the disease's hallmark cascade of inflammatory destruction.²

In periodontitis, the primary microbial agents include *Porphyromonas gingivalis*, *Aggregatibacter actinomycetemcomitans*, *Tannerella forsythia*, etc. Among these, *P. gingivalis* has been recognized as a keystone pathogen due to its ability to modify host immune responses and disrupt microbial homeostasis, leading to dysbiosis. Various virulence factors of *P. gingivalis*, such as gingipains, fimbriae, hemagglutinins, and lipopolysaccharides, have been

studied as potential vaccine targets.³ Research efforts have explored different vaccine formulations, including whole-cell vaccines, subunit vaccines, recombinant protein vaccines, DNA-based vaccines, and synthetic peptide vaccines, each with distinct advantages and limitations. The goal of a periodontal vaccine is to induce a long-lasting immune response that can either prevent bacterial colonization or neutralize their pathogenic mechanisms. Both systemic and mucosal immunization routes have been investigated to achieve adequate immune protection in the oral cavity.⁴ Animal models have demonstrated encouraging results, showing reduced bone loss and bacterial load following immunization with specific antigens derived from periodontal pathogens. However, translating these findings into successful human clinical applications remains a significant challenge due to the complexity of the oral microbiome, host variability, and ethical considerations in vaccine testing.⁵

From an immunological perspective, the induction of secretory IgA antibodies at the mucosal surface plays a crucial role in preventing bacterial adherence and colonization. Additionally, systemic immune responses, including IgG production and T-cell activation, can enhance bacterial clearance and modulate inflammatory damage. The challenge lies in identifying the most immunogenic and safe antigens that can elicit protective immunity without triggering excessive inflammation or autoimmunity.⁶ Recent advances in molecular biology, genomics, and immunoinformatics have opened new possibilities for designing multivalent and recombinant vaccines capable of targeting multiple pathogens simultaneously. Beyond prevention, periodontal vaccines may also have therapeutic potential in reducing disease progression in already affected individuals. By modulating the immune response and suppressing the overactive inflammatory pathways, vaccines could complement conventional mechanical therapy and reduce the need for repeated antibiotic use. Furthermore, considering the established link between periodontitis and systemic diseases such as cardiovascular disease, diabetes mellitus, and adverse pregnancy outcomes, effective vaccination strategies could have far-reaching health benefits beyond the oral cavity.⁷

Despite these promising perspectives, several hurdles remain before periodontal vaccines can be integrated into clinical practice. The polymicrobial nature of periodontal infection complicates vaccine design, as protective immunity against one pathogen may not prevent disease caused by others. Additionally, the oral mucosal environment presents unique challenges for antigen delivery and immune response maintenance. Variations in host genetics, oral microbiota composition, and lifestyle factors further influence vaccine efficacy. Hence, a deeper understanding of host-microbe interactions, immune regulation, and microbial ecology is essential for the successful development of periodontal vaccines. The concept of a periodontal vaccine represents a paradigm shift from conventional mechanical and antimicrobial therapy toward immune-based prevention. Although still in the experimental stages, advances in molecular immunology and biotechnology continue to bring this goal closer to clinical reality.⁸ This review aims to provide a comprehensive overview of the current developments in periodontal vaccine research, including the types of vaccines under investigation, their mechanisms of action, preclinical findings, and the challenges that must be overcome to translate this innovative concept into a practical tool for periodontal disease management. The evolution of periodontal vaccines holds great promise for the future of

preventive dentistry and could significantly contribute to reducing the global burden of periodontal disease.

IMMUNIZATION AND VACCINE DEVELOPMENT:

Immunologic response is an outcome of the mechanism in which an antigen directly or through antigen-presenting cells, recognizes lymphocytes and differentiates into effector cells and memory cells specific to that particular antigen. This response takes two forms, humoral and cell-mediated. Humoral immunity depends on the appearance of antibodies produced by plasma cells in the blood. Cell-mediated immunity depends mainly on the development of T cells that are specifically responsive to the inducing agent and are generally active against intracellular organisms. The antibody produced by effector B lymphocytes following contact with an antigen for the first time is usually of short duration and is characterized by a slow rise and rapid fall of immunoglobulin in the serum, and this response is known as the primary response. The clone of cells, which carry memory, can then be reactivated on subsequent contact with the same antigen to give rise to an accelerated, long-lasting antibody response, and this is known as a secondary response. The response can be mediated either by neutralization of microbes and toxins, opsonization and phagocytosis of microbes, antibody-dependent cellular cytotoxicity, or by phagocytosis of microbes opsonized with complement fragments.⁹

Understanding these immune mechanisms forms the foundation for vaccine development. Vaccines are designed to mimic natural infection by introducing an antigenic component, such as an inactivated or attenuated microorganism, or a purified subunit, into the body without causing disease. This controlled exposure stimulates the immune system to generate both primary and memory responses, leading to the production of specific antibodies and sensitized T cells. As a result, the immune system becomes “primed” to recognize and respond rapidly to the actual pathogen upon future exposure, thereby preventing illness or reducing its severity.¹⁰

In the late 18th century, Edward Jenner pioneered the concept of vaccination by utilizing the cross-protective effects of the cowpox virus, which poses no danger to humans. Vaccines are generally prophylactic.¹⁰

There are three main types of vaccination:¹¹

1. **Active immunization** – This involves stimulating the body’s immune system by administering killed or live-attenuated microorganisms or their products.¹¹
2. **Passive immunization** – This method provides immediate protection by transferring antibodies produced in one individual to another.¹¹
3. **DNA immunization** – In this type of vaccination, DNA plasmids containing genes that encode specific antigens are introduced into the body to trigger an immune response.¹¹

A vaccine should activate the immune system to produce antibodies without causing the actual disease in the host. An ideal vaccine should replicate the immune response produced by a natural infection while causing minimal or no side effects. It should be easy to produce, simple to administer, and economically feasible. Modern vaccine development has evolved beyond

traditional approaches, incorporating advanced technologies such as recombinant DNA methods, mRNA platforms, and vector-based systems. These innovations allow for precise antigen selection, enhanced immunogenicity, and improved safety profiles. Additionally, the use of adjuvants, delivery systems, and targeted immunization strategies further enhances the efficacy and duration of the immune response. Overall, vaccines use the body's innate immunologic memory to offer long-term protection, making them one of the most effective methods of preventing infectious diseases.¹²

EMERGING DEMAND FOR A PERIODONTAL VACCINE

The oral cavity serves as the primary entry point for infectious agents and allergens in the human body, with approximately two-thirds of all human pathogens gaining access through these routes. The body's combined mucosal surfaces cover an extensive area of around 400 m², of which the oral cavity contributes approximately 240 cm². These surfaces must be continually protected against microbial invasion, toxins, and allergens. Although humans possess a highly sophisticated and complementary immune defense system, certain microorganisms can evade these defenses and cause diseases.¹³ The challenge underlies the pressing need for the development of vaccines targeting:

1. Immune-Evasive, Tissue-Invading Bacteria

Porphyromonas gingivalis produces proteases that serve dual purposes: providing peptides essential for its growth and degrading host antibacterial components such as antibodies, complement proteins, and immune cell-derived peptides (e.g., cytokines) that promote immune responses. Additionally, this bacterium can evade local gingival immune mechanisms by invading epithelial cells and can disseminate systemically through endothelial cell invasion.¹⁴

Aggregatibacter actinomycetemcomitans possesses unique virulence factors, including leukotoxin, which specifically targets host immune cells like neutrophils and monocytes, and other molecules that suppress immune responses, ensuring bacterial survival. This pathogen also invades epithelial and endothelial cells, creating a protected niche, facilitating systemic circulation, and allowing colonization of distant tissues. Collectively, these immune-evasive strategies enable periodontal pathogens to proliferate and accumulate to critical levels, initiating tissue destruction and disease progression.¹⁴

2. REDUCING PERIODONTAL-RELATED SYSTEMIC DISEASES

Periodontal diseases are no longer considered localized lesions affecting only teeth and supporting structures; their systemic implications are increasingly recognized. They are associated with elevated levels of systemic inflammatory markers, such as C-reactive protein and fibrinogen, which predispose individuals to conditions including myocardial infarction, cerebrovascular stroke, preterm low birth weight, and pneumonia. Microbial factors also play a role—for instance, the heat shock protein (HSP) of *P. gingivalis* is an immunodominant antigen shared among many microorganisms, potentially linking periodontal infection to broader systemic effects. Therefore, developing vaccines against these pathogens could play a crucial role in preventing both local and systemic disease complications.¹⁵

Keystone Pathogens and Pathogenesis of Periodontitis: Implications for Vaccine Development:

Periodontitis is a multifactorial inflammatory disease in which a few key microbial species, known as keystone pathogens, play a disproportionate role in driving disease progression despite their relatively low abundance. Several hundred pathogens, the most common of which are

1. *Porphyromonas gingivalis*
2. *Agregatibacter actinomycetemcomitans*
3. *Tannerella forsythia*

Among these, *Porphyromonas gingivalis* is recognized for its ability to manipulate the host immune response, disrupt microbial homeostasis, and create a dysbiotic environment that favors tissue destruction. Similarly, *Aggregatibacter actinomycetemcomitans* contributes through the production of leukotoxins and other immune-modulatory factors that impair host defenses. These pathogens act in concert with other members of the oral microbiome, amplifying inflammatory responses and promoting bone and connective tissue loss. Understanding the mechanisms by which keystone pathogens evade immunity, invade tissues, and orchestrate dysbiosis provides critical insights for vaccine design. By targeting these pivotal organisms and their virulence factors, it becomes possible to prevent the establishment of pathogenic microbial communities, modulate host immune responses, and ultimately reduce the onset and severity of periodontitis.¹⁶

Virulence Traits of Periodontal Bacteria and Corresponding Immune Responses:¹⁷

PERIODONTAL VACCINE TRIALS AGAINST KEYSTONE PATHOGENS

Several experimental periodontal vaccines have been developed and tested in preclinical and clinical trials targeting key periodontal pathogens. Vaccines directed against *Porphyromonas gingivalis* have focused on its major virulence factors, including fimbriae, gingipains, and hemagglutinins, aiming to stimulate both humoral and cell-mediated immune responses to prevent colonization and tissue invasion.¹⁸ Similarly, *Aggregatibacter actinomycetemcomitans* has been targeted through leukotoxin-based vaccines, which elicit neutralizing antibodies to block its immune-suppressive effects. Other strategies have explored multivalent vaccines combining antigens from multiple periodontal pathogens to address the polymicrobial nature of periodontitis. Animal studies, particularly in mice and non-human primates, have shown promising results in reducing bacterial load, modulating host immune responses, and limiting alveolar bone loss. Although human trials are still limited, these experimental vaccines provide valuable insights into designing effective immunization strategies to prevent periodontal disease and its systemic complications.¹⁹

Some of the vaccines used for trials with these periodontal pathogens:²⁰

*Aggregatibacter actinomycetemcomitans*²⁰

- ✓ Fimbrial oligopeptide is used as an antigen
- ✓ Liposome & IL-4 expression plasmid CT was the delivery agent
- ✓ Mouse is used as a model

RESULTS:

1. Serum IgG and salivary IgA responses
2. Serum IgG: IM > PO > IN a,b
3. Salivary IgA: IN > PO > IM a,b

*Porphyromonas gingivalis*²⁰

1st trail:

- ✓ Whole cells (formalin-inactivated) used as antigen
- ✓ Hamster is the model

RESULTS:

1. Serum and salivary Ab response
2. Serum Ab: SC > PO a,b
3. No significant reduction in *P. gingivalis* colonization

2nd trail:

- ✓ Fimbriae are used as an antigen
- ✓ CT is used as a delivery agent
- ✓ Mouse is used as a model

RESULTS

1. Serum IgM, IgG, and IgA responses
2. IgG and IgA responses in saliva and fecal extract
3. Salivary IgA and IgG: IN > PO a
4. Higher antibody levels with CT

3rd trail:

- ✓ FimA (residues 55-145 or 226-337)
- ✓ Live carrier: *Streptococcus gordonii*
- ✓ Rat is the model

RESULTS

1. Serum IgG and IgA responses
2. Salivary IgA response
3. Reduced *P. gingivalis*-induced alveolar bone loss

TYPES OF PERIODONTAL VACCINES:

1. SUBUNIT VACCINES: These vaccines include specific antigens obtained from periodontal pathogens such as *Porphyromonas gingivalis*, *Tannerella forsythia*, and *Aggregatibacter actinomycetemcomitans*. The selected antigens are chosen for their capacity to trigger an immune response without causing infection. Subunit vaccines focus on targeting bacterial surface proteins, virulence determinants, or toxins associated with periodontal disease. Their mechanism involves activating the production of antibodies and memory T cells, which can recognize and neutralize these pathogens upon future exposure.²¹

2. LIVE ATTENUATED VACCINES: These vaccines utilize live but weakened strains of periodontal pathogens. Through attenuation, the pathogens are altered to reduce their virulence while preserving their antigenic characteristics. Live attenuated vaccines closely replicate natural infection, generating a robust and long-lasting immune response. However, concerns about possible reversion to virulence and adverse effects have restricted their development.²¹

3. DNA VACCINES: DNA vaccines employ plasmid DNA that encodes antigens derived from periodontal pathogens. Once administered, the DNA is absorbed by host cells, resulting in the expression of these antigens. This stimulates both innate and adaptive immune responses, including antibody production and activation of cytotoxic T cells. Although DNA vaccines are easy to produce and store, they may require adjuvants or specialized delivery methods to improve their immunogenicity.²¹

4. VECTOR VACCINES: Vector vaccines use attenuated viruses or bacteria as carriers to deliver antigens from periodontal pathogens into the host. These vectors transport the antigens to immune cells, eliciting an immune response. Viral vectors such as adenovirus or adeno-associated virus, and bacterial vectors like attenuated *Salmonella* or *Lactococcus* strains, have been explored for their potential in developing periodontal vaccines.²¹

5. MUCOSAL VACCINES: Mucosal vaccines are likely to offer greater protection against periodontitis than systemic vaccines, as they more effectively induce both IgG and salivary IgA responses in the oral cavity.²¹

Hence, the influence of periodontal vaccines extends beyond maintaining oral health. By preventing or alleviating periodontal disease, these vaccines may help reduce systemic inflammation and lower the risk of systemic conditions associated with periodontitis, such as cardiovascular disease, diabetes, and adverse pregnancy outcomes. Furthermore, better oral health can improve quality of life by minimizing pain, tooth loss, and the need for invasive dental treatments. Nevertheless, additional research is required to refine vaccine formulations, optimize delivery systems, enhance efficacy, and evaluate long-term safety and immunological memory.²²

MODE OF ADMINISTRATION OF PERIODONTAL VACCINES:

The mode of administration of periodontal vaccines plays a crucial role in determining their effectiveness, as it directly influences the type and strength of the immune response generated. Since periodontal diseases are primarily localized infections affecting the supporting structures of the teeth, both systemic and local routes of vaccine delivery have been explored to achieve optimal protection and immune activation.²³

1.SYSTEMIC ROUTE OF ADMINISTRATION:

Systemic vaccination involves delivering the vaccine through **intramuscular, subcutaneous, or intradermal injections**. These conventional methods aim to stimulate the body's systemic immune response by inducing the production of circulating antibodies, mainly immunoglobulin G (IgG). These antibodies can enter the gingival crevicular fluid, where they help neutralize periodontal pathogens and prevent bacterial colonization. Systemic vaccines also promote the activation of T-helper cells, which enhance both humoral and cell-mediated immune responses. However, one limitation of this approach is that it may not elicit strong mucosal immunity in the oral cavity, which is essential for protecting the gingival tissues against bacterial invasion.²⁴

2. LOCAL ROUTE OF ADMINISTRATION:

Local administration focuses on stimulating immune responses directly at the site of infection. Oral, intranasal, and intragingival routes are most commonly investigated for periodontal vaccine delivery. Among these, oral and intranasal vaccines are preferred due to their ability to activate mucosal immunity, particularly the production of secretory immunoglobulin A (sIgA). This antibody plays a vital role in preventing bacterial adhesion and colonization on tooth

surfaces and gingival tissues. Oral vaccines are also advantageous because they are non-invasive, easy to administer, and more acceptable to patients. However, challenges such as degradation of antigens in the digestive tract and maintaining vaccine stability in the oral environment must be addressed for effective immunization ²⁵

3. EMERGING DELIVERY SYSTEMS:

Recent advancements in biotechnology have introduced novel delivery systems to enhance the effectiveness of vaccines. These include nanoparticle-based vaccines, liposomes, and biodegradable microspheres, which help protect antigens from degradation and ensure controlled release at the target site. Additionally, mucosal adjuvants and polymer-based formulations are being investigated to enhance antigen uptake and stimulate the immune response within the oral mucosa. Such innovations may overcome the limitations associated with traditional delivery methods and pave the way for more effective periodontal vaccines in the future ²⁶

LIMITATIONS OF PERIODONTAL VACCINES:

Development of periodontal vaccines is limited by the complex etiology of periodontal diseases, which involves a wide range of bacterial species and intricate host–microbe interactions. Periodontitis is not caused by a single pathogen but by a polymicrobial biofilm, where keystone pathogens such as *Porphyromonas gingivalis* interact with other bacteria to disrupt immune homeostasis. Designing a vaccine that targets all relevant microorganisms and elicits a balanced immune response without triggering excessive inflammation remains a significant scientific challenge. Furthermore, individual differences in immune response, genetic variability, and underlying health conditions can influence vaccine effectiveness, making it difficult to achieve consistent results across populations.²⁷

In addition to biological challenges, there are practical and clinical limitations that slow the progress of periodontal vaccine development. Sustaining sufficient antibody levels over an extended time poses a challenge, potentially requiring booster doses to maintain efficacy. Contamination of vaccines is possible during production or storage, compromising their safety and effectiveness. Toxic responses to fully inactivated vaccinations may occur, necessitating careful monitoring of adverse reactions. Delivering antigens effectively to the oral cavity and maintaining local immune activation without causing tissue damage is complex. Clinical trials on humans are limited, and ethical considerations, high production costs, and the need for long-term efficacy studies further restrict advancement. Moreover, since periodontal diseases progress slowly and can often be managed with conventional treatments like scaling and root planing, the motivation for vaccine development and funding is relatively low. These factors collectively contribute to the current lack of an effective, commercially available periodontal vaccine.²⁸

FUTURE OF PERIODONTAL VACCINES:

The future of periodontal vaccines holds great promise in transforming the prevention and management of periodontal diseases, which remain among the most prevalent chronic infections worldwide. As research advances in immunology, molecular biology, and

biotechnology, there is growing potential to design vaccines that can provide long-term protection by targeting key periodontal pathogens and modulating host immune responses effectively. The ultimate goal is to develop safe, effective, and easily administrable vaccines that can prevent disease onset and recurrence, reducing the global burden of periodontal disease and its associated systemic complications.²⁹

One of the major future directions lies in the development of multivalent vaccines that target several pathogenic species simultaneously. Since periodontitis is caused by a consortium of microorganisms such as *Porphyromonas gingivalis*, *Tannerella forsythia*, and *Treponema denticola*, a vaccine that combines antigens from multiple bacteria could provide broader and more reliable protection. Advances in genomic and proteomic technologies are aiding the identification of conserved virulence factors and immunogenic proteins, such as gingipains, fimbriae, and outer membrane proteins, that can serve as potent vaccine candidates. In addition, recombinant DNA technology and synthetic peptide-based vaccines offer more precise, stable, and safe formulations compared to whole-cell vaccines.³⁰

Another promising area is the use of novel delivery systems and adjuvants to enhance vaccine efficacy. Nanoparticle-based delivery platforms, liposomes, and polymeric carriers are being studied to improve antigen stability, control release, and target immune cells more efficiently. The inclusion of mucosal adjuvants can further strengthen local immunity within the oral cavity by promoting the production of secretory IgA, which is critical for neutralizing pathogens at the gingival surface. Mucosal vaccines, particularly oral and intranasal formulations, are expected to gain importance due to their non-invasive nature, ease of administration, and ability to stimulate both systemic and local immune responses.³¹

The integration of personalized medicine into periodontal vaccine development may revolutionize preventive dentistry. Individual genetic variations, immune profiles, and microbiome compositions could be considered when designing customized vaccine strategies for each patient. Furthermore, understanding the link between periodontal disease and systemic conditions such as diabetes, cardiovascular disease, and adverse pregnancy outcomes opens new possibilities for vaccines that offer dual benefits, protecting both oral and systemic health. Research and development efforts should aim to involve all pathogens associated with periodontal disease, rather than focusing on individual strains. These innovations hold the potential to shift periodontal care from a treatment-oriented to a prevention-oriented approach, ultimately improving oral health outcomes and overall quality of life.

CONCLUSION:

Periodontal vaccines represent a promising advancement in the prevention and management of periodontal diseases, offering a potential shift from conventional treatment approaches to proactive disease control. By targeting specific periodontal pathogens and modulating the host immune response, these vaccines could significantly reduce disease incidence and recurrence. However, with the findings of associations between periodontal disease and other systemic diseases, the contemplation whether there was any merit in developing a vaccine against

periodontitis was put to rest, and research accelerated in this direction, with the focus being shifted to the prevention of the disease. Numerous studies in animal models have yielded good results in terms of improvements in serum Antibody titers, reduction in bone loss. However, none have been able to identify a sole or complete vaccine candidate suitable for human usage yet. A candidate vaccine combining various components of the microbe could be one of the best solutions that could prevent periodontal disease as such. With further refinement and clinical validation, periodontal vaccines may soon become a vital component of preventive dentistry, contributing to improved oral and overall health.

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